

THE ROLE OF THE YOUTH UNION IN INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF YOUTH

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Abstract: Education of social sciences in the higher education system based on modern requirements for the consistent and effective implementation of the state policy on youth in Uzbekistan, comprehensive support of young people, protection of their rights and legal interests, ability to take responsibility for the future of our country, enterprising, ambitious young people requires improvement of giving

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In the years of independence in our country, large-scale work was carried out to educate young people to be spiritually mature and physically healthy, patriotic and selfless, and to protect their rights and interests.

Nevertheless, life itself confirms that the most urgent issues in the life of young people, especially the work carried out on creating conditions and opportunities for unorganized youth to find their place in life, to direct them to the profession and ensure their employment, and to encourage their initiatives, are not at the level of demand.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the socialization of education, and reforms are being implemented to adapt the content of the taught subjects to the requirements of the times. We can see this in the "Law on Education" adopted by the Legislative Chamber on May 19, 2020, approved by the Senate on August 7, 2020, and the tasks set forth in the Law on the State Youth Program and State Policy on Youth. .

In particular, the contemporary requirements of social sciences in the higher education system for the consistent and effective implementation of the state policy on youth in Uzbekistan, the comprehensive support of young people, the protection of their rights and legal interests, and the education of enterprising and ambitious young people who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country. requires improvement of education based on

This, in turn, requires the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities in young people.

As President Sh.M. Mirziyoev noted - "Another issue that will never lose its relevance and importance for us is the task of raising our children as independent-minded, modern knowledge and professions with a solid life position, truly patriotic people.

Thus, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan aims to form a physically healthy, mentally mature and intellectually developed, independent-thinking young generation, to protect young people from external threats and the harmful effects of "mass culture", to provide comprehensive assistance and create conditions for the protection of the rights and legal interests of young people. It is a non-governmental non-commercial organization formed by individuals in the organizational and legal form of the union and uniting the youth of our country.

To deepen the democratic, political and economic reforms implemented in the country by the youth, to strengthen the peace and harmony in the society, to involve Uzbekistan in the process of joining the developed countries of the world and to ensure the effective protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of the young generation, to raise the moral and professional level of young men and women. , defines the essence of realizing their intellectual and creative potential.

The youth of today's world is the largest generation in the history of mankind in terms of numbers, as they make up 2 billion people. The future and well-being of our planet depends on the kind of people our children grow up to be.

In his speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized the following: "Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to show their potential, to prevent the spread of the "virus" of the idea of violence. For this, we believe that it is necessary to develop multilateral cooperation in social support of the young generation, protection of their rights and interests.

In this regard, Uzbekistan proposes to develop a generalized international legal document - the UN International Convention on the Rights of Youth - aimed at the formation and implementation of youth policy in today's conditions of rapid development of globalization and information and communication technologies.

When teaching the laws, concepts and principles of the science "Basics of Civil Society", special attention should be paid to the following:

- Nowadays, educating young people socially and politically, forming political consciousness, political vision and political culture in young people;
- wide use of interactive teaching methods in formation of creative thinking skills of students in educational institutions;
- Extensive use of advanced means of education, modern pedagogical technologies, taking into account the age, thinking, interests and outlook of students during the lesson and learning process;
- Avoid oversimplifying concepts, using old-fashioned methods and principles, and devaluing science;
- Working on an educational basis without pressure in the educational process, focusing on increasing the skills of young people to think independently and freely, conduct debates.

As the leader of our country noted: "The tasks of in-depth teaching of special subjects, the history of our country and world civilization, foreign languages and modern computer programs to children and young people have not yet been fully and qualitatively solved."

Based on the above, it is important to create an atmosphere of cooperation between students and teachers, to analyze world events, and to use mass media materials in explaining the essence of the subject "Basics of Civil Society". After all, 2009-2010 was declared by the United Nations as the year of youth communication and mutual understanding.

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The main tasks of the Youth Union are:

- to form mature, independent thinking young people who have their own life position and firm beliefs, who are capable of taking a worthy place in the life of society, becoming a decisive force and support in the processes of reforming and renewing the country, raising their political culture, legal literacy and legal consciousness;

- educating young people, especially unorganized youth, in a spiritual and moral sense and in the spirit of military patriotism, forming in them historical memory, national pride and sense of identity, involvement in current events, respect for national and universal values;

- to protect the rights and legal interests of young people, to support their aspiration to acquire modern professions, to involve them in entrepreneurial activities;

- supporting talented young people, creating conditions for them to realize their creative and intellectual potential, and involving them in scientific activities;

- formation of a healthy lifestyle, environmental culture among young people, especially non-unionized youth, widely involving them in regular physical education and sports;

- to protect young people, especially unorganized youth, from the influence of religious-extremist and other destructive organizations, from negative influences and threats coming from abroad under the guise of "mass culture", to help prevent and prevent delinquency and crime among young people, etc

Legal and natural persons can become members of the Union according to the procedure established by the Charter. That is, citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have reached the age of 14 and do not exceed 30 years of age and natural persons without citizenship who have been regularly living in the Republic of Uzbekistan can become members of the Union. At the same time, non-governmental non-profit organizations in the field of youth and enterprises, institutions and organizations related to the field of youth and other legal entities whose founding documents do not conflict with the Charter goals, tasks and program documents of the Union may also become members of the Union.

In order to fulfill the tasks listed above, the Union may adopt a program of appropriate measures in various areas of its activity.

The rights of the youth union are as follows:

- taking initiative on various issues of community life, making proposals to state authorities and management bodies;
- participation in the development of decisions of state authorities and management bodies in accordance with the procedure established by legislation;
- dissemination of information about their activities;
- establishment of mass media, publishing and printing activities;
- Organization of business entities in order to fulfill the tasks specified in the charter;
- establishing their own symbols; - conducting meetings, meetings, events, conferences, seminars and roundtable discussions on the issues of their activities; -

to open its regional structures in the territory of the republic in accordance with the legislation. The Union may have other rights provided by law.

In short, the decree specifically stipulates the establishment of the Youth Future Fund under the Youth Union of Uzbekistan and the provision of preferential loans and property leases through commercial banks at an annual rate of 7 percent for the implementation of business initiatives, startups, ideas and projects of young people. According to the decree, the households of unemployed youth with relevant skills will be assisted in the purchase of up to 20 poultry and rabbits, 5 small and 2 large cattle, their rearing and subsequent sale with return of their value in agreed periods.

This, in addition to providing employment to young people, serves to shape their entrepreneurial skills.

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